

Siligîtes: a QGIS extension to investigate mobility networks in archaeology

Thomas Andre^{1*}, Christophe Tufféry², Vincent Delvigne³

¹ Master degree student in Gustave Eiffel University, 5 Bd Descartes, 77420 Champs-sur-Marne & Géodata Paris, 6-8 Av. Blaise Pascal, 77420 Champs-sur-Marne.

² Ministère de la Culture, 182 rue Saint-Honoré 75001 Paris cedex & UMR, UMR 8068 TEMPS, MSH Mondes, 21 allée de l'université F-92023 Nanterre cedex.

³ CNRS, UMR 8068 TEMPS, MSH Mondes, 21 allée de l'université F-92023 Nanterre cedex & Service de Préhistoire, Université de Liège, Place du XX août, B-4000, Liège.

*Corresponding author

Correspondence: thomas.andre.archgeo@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

For about fifteen years, french Collective Research Projects have significantly advanced research on the origin and processing of silicites (commonly referred to as 'flint') during Prehistory. The method of inventory and characterization of these lithic resources, described from a dynamic perspective using the concept of the evolutionary chain, is now applied during systematic prospecting as well as in the inventory of reference collections known as 'lithothèques'. All this data is freely available through a dedicated webmapping platform: www.cartosilex.fr. The wealth of available data acquired in this context allows us today to fundamentally question the geography of Paleolithic 'cultures' in Western Europe from a landscape archaeology perspective.

Among this research, studies related to lithic transfer networks play a central role in better understanding the spatial occupation by prehistoric populations. Until recently, the preparatory data required to conduct these studies, as well as the analysis of the network's components, represented very time-consuming and repetitive stages. Moreover, the possibilities offered by Least Cost Path (LCP) analysis were underused, despite it becoming an essential tool for such studies by enabling the integration of topographical constraints into models of prehistoric population movements. This underuse is due to the complexity and low visibility of some of these tools, even though they are available in several GIS software packages (such as QGIS). To simplify the analysis process, we have developed a QGIS extension and propose appropriate modules and tools for prehistoric archaeology to: 1) assist in the acquisition and preparation of data for the creation of transfer networks; 2) facilitate the use of various LCP analyses by guiding users through the specific choices available; and 3) offer tools to simplify network analysis. For this purpose, we utilized the Python language, along with the tools provided by QGIS and PyQt, complemented by R scripts to access functions in the **Movecost** library. This library enables LCP-based analyses and offers a wide range of models, along with detailed explanations to avoid errors during use.

Three modules were developed to perform the analysis steps within the QGIS extension, named Siligites. The first module, **Silextracteur**, allows users to create a vector layer representing specific parts of geological formations from a specific WebFeatureService (WFS). This tool reduces the data preparation time for archaeologists by a factor of six. The second module, SilLCP, focuses on preparing the previous data to create networks, particularly those based on LCP. It enables the use of the resources provided by the R library **Movecost**, including tools for creating LCP networks, isolines, Least Cost Corridor analyses, and more. A wide variety of LCP models based on time and energy costs are also included. The third module, **Silanalyses**, is designed to assist users in analyzing the networks they have created, whether by simplifying the network to include only links with a specific distance, time, or energy cost; studying the centrality of nodes (degree and betweenness); or determining the shortest path between two nodes (with or without intermediate steps).

To test these tools, we used the example of the 'Magdalénien inférieur à Lamelles à Dos Dextre Marginal (LDDM),' a prehistoric 'culture' dated between 21.5 and 20.5 ka calBP. This 'culture' includes 13 prehistoric sites, including Lascaux, and features lithic objects that can be linked to nearly fifty geological sources. The area covered by these locations include a large part of southwestern part of France, from the Loire to the Pyrenees, and from the Atlantic Ocean to the eastern Massif Central. Using the tools developed with different datasets, we compared the results obtained by studying networks, whether using straight-line connections between locations or LCP-based networks. The two types of networks are quite similar in terms of the surfaces covered, with a margin of error of five to ten kilometers. Their nodes also display a similar level of connectivity, particularly in terms of betweenness. However, LCP-based networks offer new hypotheses, especially in topographically contrasting landscapes.

This paper focuses on the efficiency of the GIS tools compared to manual execution of the various stages of data treatment, as well as exploring the limitations, whether related to the tools themselves or more globally in the application of LCP to prehistoric archaeology. Our various tests allowed us to highlight these improvements and limits in terms of analysis provided by our QGIS extension, while demonstrating the advantages the different tools offer to researchers working on Paleolithic silicates in France, or on any other subject and period of archaeological study. In addition to providing easy access to various tools, including those for creation and analysis using LCP, the QGIS extension facilitates reproducibility of analyses and can help those interested in their future research.

Keywords: Geographic Information System, QGIS, Plugin, Python, R, Least Cost Path analysis, Spatial network analysis, Archaeology, Open Science.

Introduction

Among their common research topics, geography and archaeology share the question of flows (mobility of human groups or transport of goods) investigated through the reconstruction of the routes taken. In archaeology more specifically, these studies cover a wide variety of periods, spaces and fields, ranging from the reconstruction of ancient or medieval trade routes to hypotheses about the movement of entire populations through palaeogenetics (Gowen and De Smet 2020, Güimil-Farina & Parceró-Oubina 2015, Parceró-Oubina *et al.* 2023, McLean & Rubio-Campillo 2022). To this end, various geographical analysis tools are used, including spatial network analysis. This is based on the principle that any phenomenon (physical or social) can be expressed as a complex system, where interactions between its constituent elements influence the entire network and give it its characteristics. In terms of spatiality, understood here as 'the spatial dimension of a social reality' (Lussault, 2013), these networks are composed of nodes (places) with coordinates and links/edges between nodes (routes), making it possible to anchor flows in space and visualize the geometry of transfers within the network (Collar *et al.* 2015).

Using GIS capacities for network analysis

Since the 1990s, Information Technology developments applied to these studies (Van Leusen 1993, Herzog 2014, Verhagen *et al.* 2019, Uitermark & Van Meeteren 2021) have made it possible, thanks to Geographic Information System (GIS) software, to analyze a large amount of spatial data. They have also facilitated the automatic performance of a considerable number of calculations, enabling the modeling of spatial networks and flows at different scales. Among other things, this automation makes it possible to quickly calculate node-related indices such as the number of links passing through them (degree centrality) or the pivotal (or gateway) nature of a node within a network (betweenness centrality); all of which help to understand the architecture of the network and the degree of connectivity between its various elements.

In addition to these developments, computational tools have also focused on Least Cost Path (LCP) analysis. Particularly developed between the mid- and late 20th century (Husdal 2000, Herzog 2014, Kantner 2012, Surface-Evans & White 2012, White 2015, Whitley & Hicks 2003), LCP calculation is based on finding paths that require a minimum 'cost' of travel to get from one point to another using a grid whose cells contain a cost value (e.g., altitude, energy cost, travel time, difficulty, etc.). The process consists of two steps (Fig. 1):

1. Creating a travel cost accumulation from a cost raster and/or a Digital Elevation Model (DEM). The objective is to add the travel cost of one pixel to that of another from the starting point. This cost is independent of direction, as it starts from the chosen origin;
2. The selection of a path with the least cost variation to model the optimal route based on pre-established criteria linking a starting point to one or more arrival points.

Figure 1 - Theoretical representation of the choice of LCP between two points (based on Vaissié, 2021, Fig. 1).

When using LCPs, various parameters must be taken into account, including:

- The direction of travel (as the terrain may vary between the departure and return points);
- The directions of movement (Fig. 2A), i.e. the cells accessible from a given point (Herzog 2014 and Alberti 2019);
- The resolution of the raster used (Fig. 2B and 2 C), which must be adapted to the study area and the phenomena represented (Herzog 2014 and 2021);
- The resolution of the raster used (Fig. 2B and 2 C), which must be adapted to the study area and the phenomena represented (Herzog 2014 and 2021, Tufféry *et al.* 2018, Verhagen *et al.* 2019);
- The type of cost chosen, the value of which varies according to the slope crossed.

Numerous models have been proposed, based on mathematical formulas for the cost of moving from one raster cell to another, taking into account various factors (e.g. load carried, weight of the walker, difficulty of movement in the area covered, etc.). For more details, see Alberti (2019) and the description of the R *Movecost* library.

Figure 2 – a: Theoretical representation of possible movements for the creation of LCPs, according to Herzog 2014 (Fig. 2 and 3).

b: Representation of possible errors related to the raster grid. Offset of the LCP (in red) from the actual path (in orange) due to an over-fine mesh.

c: Representation of possible errors related to the raster mesh and problem of simplification of obstacles such as a watercourse.

Applications in archaeology

Network analyses and LCPs thus provide archaeological researchers with clues and study leads that can be compared with other information and types of data (Herzog 2012, 2014 and 2021, Verhagen *et al.* 2019). For prehistoric periods, the question of human migration is generally based on data relating to food supplies, modes of transport and the transformation of materials found at archaeological sites. These analyses – known as techno-economic analyses – seek to characterize and trace the different stages of the operational chain (Leroi-Gourhan 1964). The materials, which vary in type, may include bone tools (Gravel-Miguel and Wren 2018), colouring materials (Dayet and Lebon 2022), or lithic materials such as obsidian

(Poupeau *et al.* 2023) or silicites¹ (e.g. Angevin and Delvigne 2021, Aubry and Luis 2015, Delvigne 2016, Kantner 2012, Martin-Jarque *et al.* 2022, Murrieta-Flores 2010, Sanchez de la Torre and Mangado 2016, Sanchez de la Torre *et al.* 2025, Vaissié 2021).

In the case of lithics, which constitute the majority of Palaeolithic remains, comparing them with samples contained in georeferenced geological collections makes it possible to identify the origin of archaeological assemblages and to draw up maps of material transfers, a metonymy for human movement.

However, several limitations to these studies must be noted. Studying populations and territories dating back several thousand years while considering they remained identical can lead to errors, especially with an actualistic transposition of space from a physical point of view. For example, material sources may have been covered or completely exploited, the topography of the relief may have changed, and the known and studied archaeological sites are only a sample of human occupation sites, some of which have not been found, others may have disappeared, leaving no trace to study. Furthermore, sites whose occupations are considered contemporary on a prehistoric archaeological timescale are taken into account in the same model, which does not guarantee that the occupations were perfectly contemporary with each other. Furthermore, these occupations, which sometimes span more than a thousand years, are dated using techniques that are, at best, accurate beyond the span of a generation ($> \pm 50$ years). Lastly, the current perception of territories (*sensu* Di Méo 1998) from a cultural anthropology perspective is most likely not the same as that of past communities (Delvigne and Raynal 2021). It is therefore evident that the territories perceived and studied today by prehistorians are probably not the same as those appropriated by prehistoric peoples. As such, the archaeological record of territories, based on the study of materials, can be likened to a litho-space and considered as a network of places defined by all the sites and sources of materials that aggregate different historical and social realities (Fig. 3). Due to their reticular structure, these litho-spaces lend themselves to network analysis, and when integrated into models, LCP can contribute to a better understanding of the relationships between places.

Figure 3: Schematic representation of 'fluid territories', according to Angevin and Delvigne, 2021.

When spatial analyses involve numerous locations scattered over a very large area, they can prove to be quite tedious. Extracting and preparing the data to be analyzed in order to create networks for processing, simplification and analysis are very time-consuming and repetitive steps. Furthermore, not all archaeologists are familiar with the LCP creation tools available in GIS software (such as QGIS) or analysis software (such as RStudio). The use of these tools is therefore not necessarily user-friendly and often leads to misinterpretation and/or misuse of the available models (see criticism in Herzog 2012 and 2014, Verhagen *et al.* 2014 & 2019, Tufféry 2022).

1 The term 'silicites' refers to fine-grained, ultra-siliceous rocks ($> 90\%$ silica) (Fernandes *et al.* 2013) that were generally used as blanks/tools support during prehistory.

Creating a QGIS extension to assist in those analyses

The Siligîtes extension for QGIS is the result of work carried out with archaeologists specializing in petroarchaeological and prehistoric studies, which are part of the Collective Research Programmes (CRP) named 'Réseaux de lithothèques' (Lithotheque Networks) and the Thematic Network (TN) named 'SILEX'.

The extension is divided into different modules in line with our desire to provide easy-to-use tools that can be adapted as analyses progress, while complying with open science standards and using open source tools. The three modules that make up the extension are designed to address the various objectives and issues mentioned above:

1. The extraction of preparatory data;
2. The preparation and creation of straight line and LCP networks;
3. The analysis and simplification of these networks to answer questions about past mobility and preferential travel routes/corridors.

In addition to attempting to identify and classify the different stages of the analyses archaeologists generally carry out for their studies, we also collected their various questions concerning the implementation of the extension. Will it be more efficient than doing it manually? What is the real advantage of LCPs over straight lines, which have been used until now by some of them and are much simpler to create? What are the limitations, constraints, and drawbacks of using these tools? Do they help with the questions of reproductibility of the research archaeologists conduct, while being usable by people who are not part of the CRP and TN? We tried to answer these questions during our analysis of the results obtained after our tests in order to see whether our extension meets their requirements, as well as those of people working on other archaeological subjects and periods.

To do so, various analyses were conducted on the chrononym of the 'early Lower Magdalenian' known as the 'LDDM techno-complex', dated between 21,500 and 20,500 years BP (Langlais and Ducasse (eds.) in press).

Materials and methods

The extension and its three modules were developed primarily using the Python programming language. The aim was to use the features of QGIS software and, as far as possible, not to force the installation of additional elements beyond those already contained in the software. The extension itself has been in existence for just over a year and will continue to evolve in line with developments in QGIS, as well as feedback from current and future users.

One of the modules, SilLCP, works using resources linked to the R language, including the **Movecost** library developed by Gianmarco Alberti in 2019. This offers the possibility of using seven tools linked to LCPs, ranging from the creation of cost isolines to the creation of networks, supported by twenty-six documented models so as to understand their contexts of use and their value. It therefore seemed important to make these tools available for network creation, while retaining information and descriptions of their use in order to limit misuse (and therefore misinterpretation). Another advantage of this library is the possibility of integrating different movement variables, such as the speed or weight of the walker, the load carried, the type of calculation function, etc. These variables are used by certain models, particularly when the cost is expressed in energy value (calories, joules, etc.). It should be noted that an extension also called **Movecost** already exists for QGIS and provides access to these tools. However, with changes in versions of QGIS and the R version of the library (both Open Source), bugs have appeared and caused difficulties in the direct and effective use of this tool during our work. It was decided to take inspiration from the way this plugin established the link between QGIS and R, as well as from existing scripts, in order to adapt and simplify them for use in archaeological studies. To create this link, it is necessary to use another QGIS extension called **Processing R Provider**, which cannot be replaced at present, requiring it to be downloaded and used beforehand.

By configuring it correctly from the QGIS options, it allows the link to be made between the R language installed on the computer and the file where the libraries are stored. It is therefore necessary to install this language and the extension beforehand, and then configure the latter. The extension allows the use of scripts in .rsx format (in R language) either from QGIS or through PyQt calls. Each script also comes with a .rsx.help file containing all the information on the variables that can be used and are used. Each LCP model is accompanied by its equation, as well as a bibliographic reference for more information on its area of applicability. For the third module, **Silanalyses**, certain **GRASS** tools available in QGIS have been mobilized. It is therefore important to activate them in order to use these analyses before launching them.

Continuing with the data used, it should be noted that the extension, particularly its first module, provides access to several layers of data for easy analysis. Some are automatically downloaded by the extension when they are loaded, including those from the French National Geographical Institute (IGN), while others are already present directly, or accessed temporarily when using certain tools.

There are four of these layers:

- The national WFS feed from the TN 'SILEX', which is automatically loaded by the module during analyses for the selection of geological formations (for more details, refer to Tufféry *et al.* 2022).
- An example of a vector layer of polygons representing extraction areas, representing natural regions² (or geotopes), used as the preferred scale for spatial analysis by archaeologists from the CRP 'Réseaux de lithothèques' and the TN 'SILEX'. It should be noted that due to the number of factors involved in defining these regions, it was difficult to draw their boundaries with precision. After discussion with the archaeologists using the tool, it became clear that having access to this data in general terms was more than sufficient for their research, even if it meant (re)checking in advance whether the geological formation they were looking for was located in the correct natural region.
- A vector layer of administrative entity polygons representing French departments, taken from the IGN's BD TOPO database. As the national WFS feed is composed of departmental feeds, their names can be used to identify the department to which the geological formation belongs. For the time being, it is necessary to use French departments (or a layer based on these names), but other administrative entities may be used in the future with the development of the WFS stream beyond metropolitan France by the TN (e.g. Belgian provinces, German Länder, etc.);
- A point vector layer containing the names and locations of French municipalities. These are used by archaeologists to locate specific types of silicites within larger geological formations. It was possible to use the layer of municipal boundaries in France from the IGN's BD TOPO database, extracting the centroid of each of these municipalities. The aim was not to obtain the exact position of the center of these municipalities, but rather an approximate position in order to then create a selection buffer. The decision to use the centroid seemed to be the simplest and most effective solution. Another point layers can be used if necessary.

The data related to the LDDM techno-complex used for the tests presented in the Analysis and Discussion section comes from thirteen archaeological sites located in the south of France: Le Taillis des Côteaux, l'abri du Blot, l'abri André Ragout, La grotte Bouyssonie, Solvieux, Lachaud, Lascaux, La Reverdit, L'abri du Houleau, Combe Cullier, Pégourié, Le petit Clou Barrat and the Scilles cave. Thanks to petroarchaeological work, the associated lithic artifacts have made it possible to identify nearly fifty sources/deposits of materials (for more details, see Delvigne *et al.*, in press) (Table 1). These sixty or so locations (sites and deposits) cover a large area stretching from the Loire to the Pyrenees and from the Atlantic Ocean to the east of the Massif Central (for more details, see Langlais 2020).

2 This layer is the result of vectorisation work on the map available at the following URL: https://fr.wikipedia.org/wiki/R%C3%A9gion_naturelle_de_France

Reference city (< 10 km) and French department number	Common name	Stratigraphic origin	Géotope
Brignac la Plaine (19)	Jaspéroïdes	Sinemurien	Bassin de Brive_ouest
Puy d'Arnac (19)	Jaspéroïdes	Hettangien	Bassin de Brive_Sud
Pom Bonne (24)	Bergeracois noir de Pom Bone	Campanien	Bergeracois_Central
Creysse (24)	Bergeracois	Campanien	
Bergerac 24)	Bergeracois	Pleistocène (alluvions)	Bergeracois_Dordogne
Meusnes (41)	Turonien inférieur de la basse vallée du Cher	Turonien	Boischaud nord_Cher
Moulin sur Céphon (36)	Turonien inférieur à dendrites	Turonien	Boischaud nord_Nahon
Néret (36)	Jaspes du Chaumois	Hettangien	Boischaud sud_est
Chalais (36)	Tertiaire "calcdonieux"	Priabonien	Brenne_sud-ouest
Audignon (40)	Silex d'Audignon	Maastrichtien	Chalosse
Confolens (16)	Jasperoïde de Confolens	Hettangien	Charentes Limousine_Confolentais
Bossay sur Claise (37)	Grand Pressigny à bryozoaires	Turonien	
Abilly (37)	Grand Pressigny	Turonien	Chatelleraudais_Claise
Coussay-les Bois (16)	Turonien supérieur de Coussay	Turonien	Chatelleraudais_Creuse
Saint Pierre de Maille (86)	silex des Cottés	Rupélien	Chauvinois_Est
Lespugues (31)	Petit Pyrénées	Missing in the WFS	Comminges
Montsaunès (31)	Montsaunès	Missing in the WFS	
Sigeac (11)	Bages-Sigeac	Missing in the WFS	Corbières
Libourne (33)	Teriaire	Rupélien	Entre-deux-Mers
Libourne (33)	Senonien noir	Pleistocène (alluvions)	
Issoire (63)	Tertiaire de Limagne	Langhien	Grande Limagne
Montgaillard (9)	Montgaillard	Missing in the WFS	Haut-Adour
Gavaudun (47)	Silex de Gavaudun	Coniacien	Haut-Agenais_Lemance
Castelmoron sur Lot (47)	Tertiaire "calcdonieux"	Aquitaniens	Haut-Agenais_Lot
Vayrac (46)	Jurassique des Causses	Missing in the WFS	Haut-Quercy_Dordogne
Beaulieu sur dordogne (19)	Tertiaire d'Aurillac	Pleistocène (alluvions)	
Turennes (19)	silex de Turennes	Bathonien	Haut-Quercy_nord
Saint-Léger (17)	Grain de Mil	Coniacien	Haute-Saintonges
Antigny (86)	Bathonien de la Benaize	Bathonien	Montmorillonais_Benaize
Doussac (86)	Doussac	Bathonien	
Jouet (86)	Bathonien de Jouet	Bathonien	Montmorillonais_Gartempe
Angles sur l'Anglin (86)	Bathonien de l'Anglin	Bathonien	
Antigny (86)	Bathonien indifférencié	Bathonien	
Civeaux (86)	Bajocien de Civeaux	Bajocien	Montmorillonais_Vienne
Civeaux (86)	Bathonien de la Vienne	Bathonien	
Mussidan (24)	Bergeracois du Mussidanais	Campanien	Mussidanais
Mussidan (24)	Alluvions vallée de L'isle	Pleistocène (alluvions)	
Mussidan (24)	Silex à rhomboèdres	Campanien	
Périgueux (24)	Sénonien noir	Santonien	Périgord central_Isle
Périgueux (24)	Sénonien noir	Campanien	
Belvès (24)	Sénonien blond	Santonien	Périgord noir_Dordogne
Belvès (24)	Sénonien noir	Campanien	
Tamniès (24)	Sénonien blond	Santonien	Périgord noir_Est
Peyzac-le-Mouster (24)	Sénonien noir	Santonien	Périgord noir_Vézère
Peyzac-le-Mouster (24)	Sénonien noir	Campanien	
Montignac (24)	Sénonien noir	Coniacien	
Gien (45)	Silex de Gien	Turonien	Puisaye
Fumel (47)	Fumelois	Missing in the WFS	Quercy Blanc_ouest
Cabrereets (46)	Tertiaire	Missing in the WFS	Quercy Central_Célé

Table 1 - Summary of geotopes identified in LDDM sites.

Created Modules and Results

Silextracteur

The first module is called **Silextracteur**. Its purpose is to facilitate the preparation and extraction of polygons from geological formations at the start of analysis. The module itself can be considered a single tool, following a procedure comprising various steps as carried out by archaeologists from the CRP "Réseaux de lithothèques" and the TN 'SILEX'. These steps include extracting, from the national WFS published by the TN, the boundaries in the form of polygons of a specific geological formation, most often linked to a natural region/geotope and containing a given type of material. Due to the relative heterogeneity of silicites within the same geological formation, it is possible to restrict the extraction area by cutting the polygon around a specific municipality (radius of +/-12 km around their centroid). The tool allows each of the geological formations extracted in a single or several distinct layers that can be used for analysis³.

Using this module, it was possible to obtain, in a single layer, over 50 silicate geological formations identified as being linked to the LDDM techno-complex. The study area covered extends from the Atlantic Ocean to the east of the Massif Central and from the Loire to the Pyrenees (Fig. 4).

3 Here, as with the other modules, you can refer to the user guide available in the module for more details on the procedures to follow.

Figure 4 - Overview of the study area and the 49 geological formations extracted with the first plugin.

SiILCP

The second module, called SiILCP, meets the needs related to network creation and the use of LCP. It consists of two parts: the first contains generic tools, and the second provides access to the tools in R's **Movecost** library.

General preparation tools

- 1) The first tool in the module allows to isolate a specific point in a point vector layer and create a second layer with all the other points as the destinations.
- 2) The second tool allows to create a point vector layer from a polygon vector layer and a reference point in another layer. Most of the tools used to create routes are based on two points rather than one point and one polygon. From the polygon layer, it is possible to create a layer containing the centroids, the closest points and/or the furthest points from the reference point for each entity.
- 3) The third tool allows to create networks of straight lines between all the points in the selected input layer, or between a single point and destination points.
- 4) Quick access has also been added for some of **Movecost**'s most commonly used tools (see below) for ease of access.

Movecost's tools

- a. **Movecost**: This tool calculates cumulative costs based on the slope, as well as least-cost paths (LCP) and least-cost corridors (LCC). Its purpose is to create a vector layer of LCP-type lines for the outward journey (and return journey if necessary) between a point

of origin and one or more points of destination. The function also creates a vector layer of lines with isolines around the starting point based on a manually defined interval, or automatically based on the calculation of 1/10th of the total cost (Fig. 5).

Figure 5 - Example of **Movecost** results. LCP outward journey in green, LCP return journey in blue and isochrones in red, with an interval calculated for one hour value.

- b. **Movebound**: This tool uses a raster to calculate the limits of a given walking cost based on the slope around one or more points. Its purpose is to calculate the contour line corresponding to a specific cost in terms of time or energy (Fig. 6).

Figure 6 - Example of **Movebound** results. Isochrone around the four locations (white dots), representing the limit accessible within a 3-hour walk or less.

- c. **Movecorr**: This tool calculates the least costly corridor between two points. The tool will calculate the Least Cost Corridor (LCC) raster file from the sum of the cost rasters between two points or all selected points. If the corridor is created between two points, the vector layers of the LCP lines for the outward and return journeys will be created. If several points are analysed, only the LCC raster will be created (Fig. 5c).

Figure 7 - Example of **Movecorr** results. Forward LCP in green, backward LCP in blue, and LCC in colour gradient.

- d. **Movealloc**: This tool allows to perform a cost distribution analysis. Using a certain number of origin points, a cost distribution grid is produced; each cell in the cost distribution grid is assigned an integer indicating the origin point closest to that cell. The aim is to identify which point is closest in terms of travel cost among the pixels, and then represent the distribution of the raster in the form of a vector layer of polygons and a raster (Fig. 8).

Figure 8 - Example of **Movealloc** results. Isochrones around sites (1/10th of total cost) and distribution of raster pixels according to different colours.

- e. **Movecomp**: This tool allows LCPs to be calculated using different cost functions and displayed on the same visual medium for comparison purposes. It allows visual comparison of the paths taken by LCPs with three different equations (Fig. 9).

Figure 9 - Example of **Movecomp** results. Forward LCP (shaded in green) and reverse LCP (shaded in blue) linked to different functions in relation to time and energy expended.

- f. **Movenetw**: This tool calculates LCPs between multiple origins. The result is an LCP network connecting all the points, or each point to its nearest neighbour (Fig. 10).

Figure 10 - Example of **Movenetw** results. White lines: closest neighbours; Black lines: complete network.

- g. **Moverank**: This tool calculates the least expensive route between a starting point and a destination and, more importantly, determines the N least expensive routes between these two points. Similar to **Movecost** (see above), the advantage is that, using the same model, it is possible to observe the different travel options represented by the LCPs between one point and one or more other points contained in a vector layer of points. However, the tool only creates a vector layer of the most optimal LCP lines, as well as a raster file representing the LCC (Fig. 11).

Figure 11 - Example of **Moverank** results. Six most optimal LCPs (from large to thin line) between two locations, as well as the LCC created.

For more details on how to use the tools presented, as well as on **Movecost's** functions, please refer to the user guides available in the module.

Various networks have been created to test the module's functionality (Fig. 12). The LCP networks were created using the IGN's ALTI@ 25M database, whose pixels are initially 25 m square. For this project, they were resampled to obtain pixels measuring 100 m on each side, for reasons of processing and calculation time.

We created the straight-lines network using the tool included in the SiILCP module, that simply create lines between all the points of the layer, and the **Movenetw** tool for the LCP, using Tobler's off-road model (Tobler 1993, Minetti *et al.* 2006). This model is similar to the classic Tobler hiking function, generally used by LCP construction tools, but where the walking speed is more significantly reduced depending on the slope, making it more suitable for a time-period with archer travel conditions.

The networks used for the analyses are:

- Two vector layers of complete networks of LCPs and straight lines connecting all 62 locations (sites and raw material sources) of the LDDM techno-complex;
- Three vector layers of the 'line' type representing the LCPs between the Combe Cullier site (Lacave, Lot) and the other sites of the LDDM techno-complex, as well as the centroid and closest and furthest points from the silicate sources corresponding to the archaeological artefacts unearthed at the site (Langlais *et al.* in press).

Figure 12 - Top (1a and 1b): comparison of networks created using **Movecost** tools (left) and straight lines (right). Bottom: comparison of the sub-networks linked to the site of the Combe Cullier, obtained based on points representing polygons: straight lines (2a) and LCPs (2b) to reach the centroids of the polygons, LCPs to reach closest points (2c) and the furthest point (2d) of the polygons. Archaeological sites (black rings) and deposits (white circles) are represented with the white circle, while the different edges are classified according to their length, from white (shortest) to red (longest)

Silanalyses

Once the network has been created, the third module, **Silanalyses**, offers various tools to simplify the obtained results (if necessary) and perform centrality analyses. This module is divided into three tools:

- 1) A tool to merge different parts of networks if successive analyses were needed. After selecting the relevant vector line layers, the module re-indexes the entities before adding them to a new layer. Using location selection, the module searches for completely identical links in the network, allowing some of the possible duplicates to be removed. It should be noted, however, that this tool is not infallible, and that it is better to carry out an initial sorting upstream as a precaution, whether this is simply visual or by looking at the start and end points of the links created, in order to identify duplicates. Similarly, it is important to check whether the different nodes in the network are indeed identical. It has been found that even if the links appear to arrive at exactly the same place visually, this is not necessarily the case when analyzing the nodes in the network. This error is due to the fact that if different analyses were carried out, the nodes might not be placed at exactly the same coordinates (even if the difference is tiny) and/or are not recognized as identical. It is therefore necessary to slightly move the nodes in case of problems using the vertex modification and point snapping options in QGIS.
- 2) A tool to simplify and analyze network centrality. Three threshold value options are available, linked to the cost values and metadata from **Movecost** tool outputs. Note that this tool can be used for any network, whether or not it was created with **Movenetw**, as long as it has at least one field in the attribute table that gives a value to the links in one of the compatible formats. The tool compares the value of each link with the threshold and only keeps those that are equal to or less than this value. Once the network has been simplified, a **GRASS** tool is used to automatically calculate the centrality (degree and intermediary) of the nodes.
- 3) A tool to help visualize the shortest or fastest path between two points in the network, whether or not it passes through predefined intermediate stages. The aim is to identify, within a very dense network, a possible path with the lowest cost in terms of distance or time traveled in order to see if it passes close to other nodes (locations) in the network.

The networks created previously were analyzed using the second tool in this module. The results of the analyses are presented in the following section.

Analysis and discussion of results

Comparison of the use of the extension versus manual steps

Several parameters can be compared to see the advantages and/or disadvantages of the extension and its modules compared to performing the processing steps manually. The simplest approach was to look at the characteristics of each of the modules.

For **Silextracteur**, the most important parameter is the number of actions to be performed and/or the time required to extract the geological formations used in the studies. After conducting several tests, it appears that the module can reduce the number of steps required by almost half, from selecting the tools to be used to moving the map in the GIS and preparing the function parameters. To select a type of geological formation, around forty manipulations were necessary, and even more in some cases. The module allows the same operation to be performed in about twenty manipulations. One of the CRP researchers conducted a test using one of his datasets without necessarily being completely familiar with **Silextracteur**. Manually extracting all the data he needed took nearly six hours, while the module reduced this time to about half an hour. The main limitation identified is that the tool is specifically designed for WFS from the TN 'SILEX', but more data related to other territories and/or materials could be added in the future.

For **SilLCP**, two factors must be taken into account, depending on the parts of the module. The network preparation tool (isolation of a point) reduces the number of actions from around twenty actions in five minutes of processing time to just five actions that can be completed in less than a minute. The second tool (creation of a point to represent polygons) reduces the number of operations from around ten or even twenty, depending on the type of point chosen (centroids or

nearest/furthest points), to five or eight operations that can be completed in less than two minutes. As for the part of the module related to **Movecost**, it is more difficult to evaluate these parameters. Here, the main advantage is that this R library can be used directly from QGIS, eliminating the need to switch between the two software programs for analysis. The module also has the advantage of automatically creating files that can be used in QGIS, containing the metadata of the parameters used, without having to modify them from R. In addition to the need to install and initialize R, which can be complicated (especially on Mac), the main limitation identified remains the time required to perform analyses on networks covering a very large geographical area.

For small-scale studies with few points, the analysis remains fairly fast. For example, it takes less than five minutes to create an LCP network between four points over an area of approximately 845 km² with a pixel grid of 100 metres ($\pm 5,500,000$ px).

On the contrary, it took nearly 35 hours of processing (spread over three analyses, as it required too much computing power to be carried out in one go) to create the network connecting the 62 locations (sites and material sources) of the LDDM techno-complex, covering an area of more than 197,500 km² with a pixel grid of 100 metres ($\pm 19,900,000$ px). The main cause of the increase in calculation time is the number of pixels in the DEM, since the calculation of the cumulative displacement cost is an integral part of the creation of LCPs. Doubling the pixel size reduces the calculation time by almost half, but leads to a decrease in the accuracy of the model. Next in logical order are the number of LCPs to be calculated and lastly the distance between points, leading to longer calculations.

For **Silanalyses**, advantages in terms of number of manipulations/time can also be noted. The network merging tool is difficult to reproduce without access to the QGIS Python console, particularly for the entity reindexing step. With the module, this operation can be performed in less than eight manipulations and takes approximately one minute, depending on the number of links to be processed. As for the network simplification tool, the module reduces the number of manipulations from around twenty in ten minutes to less than ten, with results in just over a minute. Lastly, the network route search tool reduces the number of steps from around twenty to less than ten (including the preparation of start/end/intermediate point layers) and the processing time from around ten minutes to less than three minutes.

The main limitation of this module, in addition to the need to activate **GRASS**, remains the need to pay attention to the layers used in the various tools, whether it be the fields that can be used for the simplification tool or the number of points present/selected for the route search.

Influence of terrain on network and comparisons between distances and journey times

Comparison of straight line and LCP networks

The first comparative study conducted between straight line networks and LCP networks aimed to examine the spatial proximity of the links that compose them. Straight lines are easier to create and can be convenient for large scale studies in plains or less rugged areas. LCPs, in the other hand, are much more time-consuming to create for medium to large scale analyses, but are more interesting to take into account the impact of the topography in the spatial structuring of past populations, especially if large obstacles exist or for precise scale analysis. The objective was to consider the extent to which terrain can cause routes to deviate and thus influence spatial models. We decided to draw inspiration from the work carried out by Gowen and De Smet (2020), as well as various studies conducted by Herzog (2021) to try to assess those parameters, but instead of comparing the route taken in the field with the LCP or with existing roads, we used buffers around the straight lines to observe which LCP segment(s) were included. Different buffer values were tested ($t = 1$ m, 100 m, 1.0 km, 5.0 km and 10.0 km, see below for more details), allowing the links in the LCP network to be divided according to their overlap with the network of straight lines. The overlap rate is expressed in Table 2 as a percentage of the length of the links in the LCP network.

	Buffer distances				
Network used	1m	100m	1km	5km	10km
All nodes	10572 (2%)	396928 (64%)	596464 (95%)	620483 (99,6%)	622593 (99,95%)
Between sites	52 (0,25%)	2745 (13%)	13567 (65%)	19961 (96%)	20358 (98%)
From the Combe Cullier site	3 (0,1%)	262 (8%)	1587 (50%)	2912 (91%)	3114 (97%)

Table 2 - LCP network segments located in the buffer zone of the straight-line network links established according to the same corresponding criteria.

This analysis leads to several conclusions:

1. For a buffer of 1 m, which is equivalent to a near-perfect match between straight lines and LCPs, the overlap rate is very low ($\leq 2\%$), with differences explained by the number of network links, intersecting small portions of the routes, but none of the entire modeled routes. It should be noted, however, that in our case this buffer value is of little interest due to the resolution of the DEM in question (1 px = 100 m) – and therefore the algorithmic bias inherent in the calculations – and the difference in the morphology of the relief between prehistory and the present day;
2. For a buffer of 100 m, corresponding to the scale of the DEM used (remember that LCPs most often pass through the center of pixels), the results are highly variable, ranging from more than 50% to less than 10% of the link length retained. This difference can again be explained by the number of links that make up the network and, above all, by their density and the space they cover. This is clearly apparent for the different types of networks tested, with a much higher overlap rate for the complete network of places than for the star network (ego-network) linked to the Combe Cullier site;
3. For a buffer of 1.0 km, corresponding to the minimum possible detour when traveling short distances to avoid an obstacle, all results are above 50%, with variations depending on the number of links and the density of the network;
4. For a buffer of 5.0 km, associated with an average detour to avoid an obstacle, the cross-checking results are always above 90%;
5. Lastly, with a buffer of 10.0 km, representing a significant detour, this rate rises to over 95%, or even close to 100%.

These results suggest that, for a relatively flat area, the margin of error is between 5 and 10 km when using straight lines instead of LCPs to model a transfer network. The non-intersecting portions of the routes, representing the most significant deviations, are mainly due to the relief. This is the case, for example, in the Massif central, near the Pyrenees and for some valleys and rivers (Fig. 13). While for reasons of calculation time, straight-line networks in plains (e.g. in sedimentary basins) seem sufficient when studying transfers over long distances (here on the scale of a large quarter of France), this is not true in rugged areas (e.g. mountain ranges). In this case, it seems more relevant to create LCP networks and compare them to straight-line networks in order to better understand how certain obstacles may or may not have played a role in the spatial structuring of past populations, especially if large obstacles are present or for precise scale analysis. Due to their vast number and the difficulty to insure the pairing (straight lines and LCPs), we were unable to compare each pair of paths across the entire network (or at least the one passing through the Massif central), and see the real difference in terms of distance and of order of the roads (Prieto *et al.* 2016). However, we were still able to conduct some similar smaller-scale analyses, which we present below, and we plan to conduct similar study in the future.

Figure 13 - Different cases of high deviation of LCPs from straight-lines network. Archaeological sites and deposits are represented with the white circle, while the edges are classified according to their deviation.

Comparison of the choice of point to represent a polygon for the creation of networks and importance in travel time analyses

Since the **SiLCP** module allows three types of points (centroids, nearest points and furthest points from a reference point) to represent geological formation polygons, it was necessary to quantify the impact of choosing one of them when establishing models. As it was difficult to carry out this analysis on the entire network of sites in the LDDM techno-complex, particularly when using points other than centroids, since there is no reference point (and therefore no nearest or furthest point) within a multipolar network, this study was carried out using the example of the silicite transfer network established for one of the archaeological sites in the corpus: Combe Cullier (Lacave, Lot). This site has the advantage of being relatively central to the entire geographical network, as well as having lithic artifacts associated with 19 of the identified geological formations. We therefore created three ego-networks based on this site (Table 3).

Nodes used	Distance in straight line from the Combe Cullier site		Distance with LCPs from the Combe Cullier site		Nodes used	Journey time (round trip)with LCP (12 hours represents maximum walking time in one day)			
	< 100 km	> 100 km	< 100 km	> 100 km		< 24h (2x12h) 2-3 days trip	< 48h (2x24h) < 1 week trip	< 96h (2x48h) < 2 weeks trip	> 96h > 2 weeks trip
Closest	20	11	19	12	Closest	2	13	5	11
Centroid	20	11	18	13	Centroid	2	11	7	11
Furthest	19	12	17	14	Furthest	0	12	8	11

Table 3 - Comparison of the number of links in the Combe Cullier networks in terms of distance (left) and time (right).

Before describing the results obtained, some clarification is needed regarding the categories defined in the tables produced. Firstly, most studies of material supply rarely focus on the furthest point (representing the maximum distance traveled to obtain resources); the most commonly used points are centroids (or at least a theoretical point considered central by the analyst) (Delvigne *et al. in press*, Prieto *et al.* 2016, Sanchez de la Torre *et al.* 2025, Vaissié 2021) and, to a lesser extent, the nearest points (Andre, 2023). Secondly, the arbitrary distance limit of 100 km usually represents, in prehistoric archaeology, a theoretical distance beyond which significant travel to access resources is to be expected (for a critique, see Delvigne *et al.* 2021). With regard to time categories, and in particular the equivalences between walking time without breaks and total travel time, it is possible to draw on certain ethnographic examples presented by R. L. Kelly (2013). Depending on the hunter-gatherer populations considered, they can travel a maximum of 20 to 30 km in a day, or for nearly 8 to 10 hours, to reach a specific area. Thus, 24 hours of walking (breaks not included) in a model corresponds to a journey of two to three days of walking, 48 hours of walking to nearly a week of travel, and 96 hours of walking to expeditions of just under two weeks.

The results show that, in terms of distance traveled, the type of point chosen does not have a significant influence on the links created. This is partly due to the accuracy of the petroarchaeological analyses carried out beforehand (Delvigne 2016) and the methods used to map silicate formations (Tufféry *et al.* 2022). By focusing only on the centroids and the closest points, no difference is noticeable for straight lines, while only one location exceeds the 100.0 km limit with LCPs. In terms of travel time, the variations are slightly greater, with two locations going from less than a week's travel to more than a week, but less than two. However, the values associated with those accessible in a two- to three-day round trip, as well as those requiring more than two weeks, remain fixed, with the latter showing the same values as for locations more than 100 km from the site.

Once again, the study of the most distant points is not one of the most commonly used in prehistoric archaeology. However, it is in this category that, logically, the variations are the greatest, whether in terms of distance for straight lines and LCP or time for the latter. For Combe Cullier, it thus appears that no location is less than two to three days round trip from the site.

Although these results are influenced by various factors, such as the general shape of the geological formation and the parameters of the extraction, they allow for three observations:

1. The point representing the polygons is important, particularly when the time or distance categories are small, or when seeking minimum, average, or maximum values for material acquisition. However, this accuracy depends not only on the models, but also on the degree of accuracy of the input data (see petroarchaeological studies, Herzog 2014 and Kantner 2012).
2. It is important to take travel time into account, as this can make certain locations more accessible than their distance from the reference point would suggest. Those below the 100 km limit can be completed within a fairly wide time frame ranging from half a week to nearly two weeks. Those contrasts in time values call into question the site-centered view of archaeological interpretations based on a division of space in terms of distance and a categorization of materials in terms of local, semi-local (or regional), and distant availability. This leads to a whole range of new hypotheses relating to the mobility of groups in this intermediate space (Beaudry and Parno 2013, Vaissié 2021).
3. As a corollary, these analyses show the importance of the distance and time thresholds chosen in the development of site-centered models, particularly when journeys have values close to these thresholds.

Comparison of network closure based on specific distance and time values

The final study we carried out concerned the differences in network closure (i.e., degree of connectivity) for straight lines vs. those created using LCP. The aim is to determine the minimum distance and time values for paths between different concentrations of locations (i.e., clusters) in order to define the minimum accessibility limits from a site to its linked sources.

Four distance values were selected, representing distance limits specific to the LDDM techno-complex (for more details, see Delvigne *et al.*, in press). These offer different levels of network closure, which allow archaeological data to be interpreted in their spatial context.

The aim of our test was to compare the results of the straight-line and LCP network models, to see if there were any notable differences, and to try to define time limits for the LCPs corresponding to the levels of closure.

- Level 1 (threshold value for $k = 12$ km) (Fig. 14): Theoretical maximum limit of the so-called 'local' raw material acquisition area (i.e., linked to daily expeditions including return trips to the site), applicable to both straight lines and LCPs (Fig. 8a). The networks obtained for the value $k = 12$ km are very similar, connecting the same number of points in twelve clusters. It is interesting to note that this network partition is similar to that obtained independently for LCPs with a walking time constraint of 4 hours, i.e., 8 hours round trip, which can be considered a feasible daily trip (Kelly 2013). In our case, this confirms the value of 12.0 km as the limit of the local domain.

Figure 14 - Networks obtained for a value of $k = 12$ km, corresponding to the limit of the local raw material acquisition domain. From left to right: value of $k = 12$ km for straight lines and LCPs, value of $k = 4$ h for LCPs.

- Level 2 (threshold value for $k = 24.5$ km) (Fig. 15): Shortest straight-line distance identified for direct acquisition of raw materials known for the LDDM techno-complex⁴. This model is consistent with the 'reality' of the archaeological data due to the fact that it is based on the lithic assemblages (for more information, see Delvigne *et al.* in press). From the point of view of the degree of betweenness of the nodes, the three models are similar, except the high variability within the 'Périgord' cluster, which is linked to the presence of differentiated outward and return LCPs, compared to those calculated in the straight-line network where the return journey is identical to the outward journey.

4 Note that this value is initially equal to $k = 29$ km in Delvigne *et al.* (in press). This difference of 4.5 km results from the way in which the module's tools extracted and represented the centroid of the geological formation concerned by this distance limit.

Finally, it should be noted that this level of network partitioning can be achieved, in terms of time, with journeys of less than 9 hours, representing round trips that can last at least two days (18 hours) and therefore journeys that can last up to three days to allow humans to rest and/or extract materials. This could reflect logistics-type mobility.

Figure 15 - Networks obtained for a value of $k = 24.5$ km, corresponding to the greatest known minimum straight-line distance for direct acquisition of raw materials for the LDDM techno-complex (highlighted in red).

From left to right: value of $k = 24.5$ km for straight lines, equivalent for LCPs with $k = 25$ km and $k = 9$ h.

- Level 3 (threshold value for $k = 79$ km) (Fig. 16): The shortest straight-line allowing us to integrate all materials with high centrality (found in large quantities at most sites) into our network (Fig. 11)⁵. The main difference between the two networks is that with this threshold, one of the materials with high centrality (Coniaco-Santonian from Haute-Saintonge known as 'Grain de Mil') is not connected in the LCP network. This link appears for a threshold value increased by one kilometer, i.e., 80 km. At the spatial scale at which the work is being carried out, this difference remains anecdotal.

In terms of the degree of betweenness, this appears to be similar between the two types of networks, with a reduction in contrasts within the clusters defined above (particularly at level 2, supra). Logically, there are very high values at the nodes connecting the 'Southern Paris Basin' and 'Périgord' clusters. This network topology corresponds more or less to a time limit of 27 hours, representing round trips which, with breaks, can be reduced to journeys of nearly a week.

5 This value differs from that reported in the article by Delvigne *et al.* (in press), where the link length was originally equal to $k = 72$ km. This variation stems from the city used as a reference for one of the materials with high centrality, even though the formations selected remain broadly identical.

Figure 16 - Networks obtained for a value of $k = 24.5$ km and corresponding to the minimum straight-line connection (in red) between materials with high centrality and sites in the LDDM techno-complex.

From left to right: value of $k = 79$ km for straight lines, equivalent for LCPs with $k = 80$ km and $k = 27$ h.

- Level 4 (threshold value for $k = 135$ km) (Fig. 17): Distance allowing all locations (sites and sources of raw materials) to be integrated in the network (Fig. 12). There is a notable difference between the two types of networks: locations in the Massif Central remain isolated with LCPs, whereas they are connected to the rest of the network in a straight line. This observation is very important because, from an archaeological point of view, no evidence has been found to date to support the hypothesis of an east-west crossing for the period in question. The link connecting the nodes of the Massif Central to the rest of the LCP network appears from $k = 142$ km. This time, it passes through the Loire and Allier valleys, opening up the areas north of the Massif Central, which is more in line with the archaeological data (Angevin *et al.* in press). In terms of intermediary status, we can once again observe an overall decrease in value contrast within the clusters defined above, and the presence of high values for the nodes connecting the clusters and, by definition, acting as bridges between the different hubs of the network. In terms of time, a similar network closure is obtained with a threshold value of 48 hours, i.e., a journey of approximately two weeks with breaks.

Figure 17 - Networks obtained for a value of $k = 135$ km corresponding to the minimum distance required to connect all locations (sites and lodgings) of the LDDM techno-complex (highlighted in red). From left to right: value of $k = 135$ km for straight lines, equivalent for LCPs with $k = 142$ km and $k = 48$ h.

In general, these results show that the greater the distance between the starting point and the destination, the greater the difference between straight-line networks and LCPs, and therefore the greater the values required to achieve the same network closures. However, these changes remain small at the second and third levels of closure, remaining less than or equal to one kilometer. For the fourth level, this distance is more significant, but this is due to routes that are strongly influenced by the terrain (in this case, the Massif Central), which becomes a source of new travel assumptions (Féblot-Augustins and Perlès 1992).

In terms of betweenness, the nodes of the straight line and LCP networks of the same closure level remain fairly similar overall, with variations in absolute value linked to the presence or absence of certain LCPs due to different values between outward and return journeys. This is not the case for straight lines, where outward and return journeys are represented by the same link.

The network closure thresholds can be compared with fairly specific travel time categories (one day, half a week, one week, and two weeks). This confirms the importance of taking travel time into account in archaeological interpretations, as this parameter is more relevant than the number of kilometers to be traveled.

Finally, we found that some threshold values are not the same as those in the article that served as the basis for this work (Delvigne *et al.* in press). These differences are not related to the modeling tool, but rather to the practice of selecting polygons and thus establishing the frame of reference. Hence the importance of the accuracy of the archaeological study prior to modeling.

Accuracy of the DEM and integration of other displacement factors besides terrain and time

As previously mentioned, one of the main elements in creating LCPs is the resolution of the raster, most often a DEM. In our study, we had to resample the DEM used with the help of GDAL tools in QGIS to save the new one and obtain a resolution of $1 \text{ px} = 100 \text{ m}$, for several reasons.

The main reason was related to the time and computing power required to produce so many LCPs over such a large area. The second reason is that at this scale and over long distances, the LCPs used tend to route sections of the path through the hydrographic network, judging that the additional cost of accessing these (normally inaccessible) areas is worthwhile if it allows the journey to continue with little variation in altitude, or at least less variation than around the watercourse. To ensure that this choice does not introduce variations in the modeled route, we conducted tests. Thus, on a small scale, changes in mesh size quickly lead to LCPs crossing the hydrographic network, particularly if so-called 'knight' movements (see Herzog 2021) are taken into account in the movements.

These tests also showed that despite these changes and a few problems crossing waterways, LCPs continue to use the same migration corridors, regardless of the scale considered. This behavior of the models is precisely what is important to identify in the context of archaeogeography; archaeologists are interested in multi-scale recurrences in order to observe trends: the actual paths of the past will never be found, but modeling makes it possible to identify more or less probable corridors. Since absolute precision is not the ultimate goal—and tests show that the areas crossed remain more or less the same—the routes modeled in this work provide a first source of reliable hypotheses that can be used by archaeologists. However, further analyses will need to be carried out with more computing time available and more powerful equipment to facilitate the calculations. Different adaptations of the DEM used are therefore possible. One working hypothesis, for example, would be to transform the pixels of the DEM covered by the hydrographic network into empty pixels, creating real impassable barriers above a certain width, rather than adding, subtracting, or multiplying their values. However, it would be important to take into account certain areas where passage is possible, such as fords or passages that can be crossed in small boats, even if this required significant research, particularly over a large area. A reduction in the number of possible movements to favor those known as 'queen moves' over 'knight moves' (Herzog, op. cit.) should also be considered, as the latter can result in the crossing of normally impassable barriers, such as waterways.

Regarding the limitations and repercussions of this change in DEM resolution, we are fully aware of the accuracy issues it causes, as well as their impact on the routes created, with certain passages and obstacles disappearing as the raster cells merge. We have carried out additional tests on this choice and have noted differences between paths created with the initial resolution and those created after resampling, but the latter follow roughly the same direction and remain fairly close within a 10-kilometer buffer. As our study was on such a large scale, we considered these differences to be acceptable, but a study with a more precise scale, as well as more time and computational resources, is needed to improve the networks created, refine our study hypotheses, and better identify the impact of this change of scale in our DEM (Herzog 2021, Kantner 2012).

It is worth mentioning other factors related to travel that were not taken into account in this study, the first being the model used to calculate the LCPs. To create the networks for this study, it was decided to use Tobler's off-path hiking function (Tobler 1993, Minetti *et al.* 2006). This relatively easy-to-use function was chosen for this study as it takes into account the fact that travel takes place in areas where it is sometimes difficult to walk, and provides easily analyzable time values. Even though they were not used in this paper, for the reasons just mentioned, other types of functions, especially energy cost functions, are also available in the **Movecost** tools, and can be used for future comparisons and studies. These functions have the advantage of adding other movement parameters such as average movement speed, the weight of the walker, or the load carried.

However, other biological or travel factors are more difficult to take into account in this type of study or model. To name just a few, it is difficult to take into account parameters such as the number of people involved in the journey, their age, their gender (although some time functions seem to be able to integrate this variable in their models), variations in the weight of equipment between the outward and return journeys, knowledge of the terrain, or even walking habits and well-being.

On another note, and in line with what has been achieved during this work, displacement parameters related to the space covered can be integrated into the DEM used to create a more accurate cost raster by modifying the pixel values covered by these elements. Thus, for studies relating to more recent periods, several factors can be integrated, such as vegetation cover, the presence of marshes or semi-submerged areas that are difficult to cross, or even physical obstacles that are impossible to cross, such as cliffs, escarpments, or canyons.

Another type of parameter that can be integrated is temporality and seasonality. Indeed, identical journeys may not be carried out in the same way in winter or summer, whether due to issues of sunlight, temperature, or variations in vegetation, snow cover, frozen waterways, etc.

Similarly, it would be difficult to integrate factors other than physical ones, such as areas considered repulsive or attractive for obtaining materials from a cultural point of view, or simply areas whose social importance was recognized as high or low and which would distort the network in their vicinity. Further consideration of these points is needed to identify specific formulas that could be applied to DEMs to highlight these areas or, make them inaccessible. In the context of this work, it was difficult to integrate so many parameters, as the objective was to implement the extension and carry out initial tests on a dataset. The results obtained thus form a set of hypotheses that can be supplemented by future studies, fueled by advances in archaeological research and potential developments of the tool.

Conclusion and outlook

Our work has led to the development of a QGIS extension called *Siligites*, consisting of three modules containing tools designed to meet the various needs of archaeologists participating in the CRP 'Réseaux de lithothèques' works:

- **Silextracteur**, which extracts polygons of specific silicate geological formations from the WFS feeds of the 'SILEX' TN, which are used to analyze networks and the origins of materials. The module automates and simplifies the process while reducing the processing time required for this step sixfold;
- **SilLCP** offers tools that can be used for network studies, but also facilitates access to and use of the tools in R's *Movcost* library. The tool allows the user to create several LCP networks to compare with straight-line networks
- **Silanalyses** consists of various tools that facilitate the processing and simplification of networks in order to analyze their degree of connectivity and the centrality of nodes.

Analyses conducted using these tools have shown that straight-line and LCP networks use similar traffic spaces in areas where the terrain varies little. On the contrary, LCPs provide new hypotheses for movement in more rugged areas, where straight-line modeling does not allow for this. It was also possible to see the importance of comparing routes in terms of time rather than distance, leading to a greater variety of archaeological hypotheses. Lastly, LCPs offer new travel hypotheses by taking into account obstacles such as mountain ranges, unlike the straight lines used until now by the CRP.

It should be noted here that the WFS flows of the 'SILEX' TN will continue to evolve, requiring updates to the tools so that they remain usable. In this regard, an upgrade to the tool may involve the addition of data concerning other countries. Similarly, the network analyses carried out have provided initial data on the proximity between those composed of straight lines or LCPs, as well as on the contributions of the latter in the analyses. More in-depth studies could supplement these results, either by using other functions, more precise DEMs or by integrating other travel factors into the cost raster. As such, it would be interesting to create other LCP networks, using analyses based on energy costs, or even incorporating principles such as the attractiveness of certain areas compared to others into the DEM pixel values in order to identify possible route deviations. Finally, in addition to creating the extension and its modules, we were able to test the tool with a specific dataset from the LDDM techno-complex. The results are conclusive, and it is now possible to apply the processes developed to any other dataset.

Acknowledgements

The authors would like to thank the 2059 members of 'SILEX' TN, as well as the members of the associations *Archéo-Logis* and *Archéologie pour Tous*, for their involvement and contributions within the framework of the Collective Research Program *Réseaux de lithotèques*. We are particularly grateful to Jean-Paul Raynal, Paul Fernandes, Morgane de Parthenay, Mathieu Lebon, and Marie-France Creusillet for their support and constructive input.

The petroarchaeological data used in this study were obtained through the projects DEX_TER (directed by S. Ducasse and M. Langlais) from the *Labex LasCarBex*, the LAsCO project (directed by M. Langlais and S. Ducasse), as well as the APPs *Le Blot : études et travaux* (directed by V. Delvigne and J.-P. Raynal) and *Combe-Cullier* (directed by M. Langlais and A. Sécher). We also thank the directors of the ongoing excavations at *Grotte Bouyssonie* (É. Lesvignes, L. Dijkstra and M. Langlais) and *Taillis des Coteaux* (J. Primault and L. Brou), through which some of the data used here were collected.

This work is part of the training programs of the *École nationale supérieure de géographie* and *Université Gustave Eiffel*, and follows on from a Master's thesis conducted at the *Muséum national d'Histoire naturelle de Paris*.

Finally, we warmly thank the organizers of session 35 — *Mapping and modelling movement in archaeology: From least cost analysis to diffusion pathways* — at the 2025 CAA conference in Athens: Richard Hewitt, Manuel Alcaraz-Castaño, and Mike Morley, for inviting us to present our work.

Funding

This research was supported by the French Ministry of Culture through the Collaborative Research Projects (PCR) *Lithotheque Network* and *RT Silex*, as well as by the CNRS, the INRAP, Eveha and Paléotime.

The data concerning the origin of the silicites, were collected as part of projects funded by the French Ministry of Culture, the CNRS, the University of Bordeaux, the Auvergne and Nouvelle-Aquitaine Region, and the City of Brive-la-Gaillarde.

Conflict of interest disclosure

The authors declare that they comply with the PCI rule of having no financial conflicts of interest in relation to the content of the article. One author is a recommender for one Peer Community (PCI Archaeology: CT).

Data, scripts, code, and supplementary information availability

All the data and tools to reproduce the results are available in the archive where this paper was downloaded. It contains the article you are reading, the various figures and tables that illustrate it, the data obtained during our research enabling the results presented to be reproduced, and a copy of the module we created and used to obtain them. Consult the README.md file for more information and details on the metadata.

Other access to the module Siligite to reproduce the Results:
QGIS repository: <https://plugins.qgis.org/plugins/siligites>
GitLab: <https://gitlab.com/Thomas.Andre.Archgeo/Siligites>

References

- Alberti G. (2019). Movecost: An R package for calculating accumulated slope-dependent anisotropic cost-surfaces and least-cost paths. *SoftwareX*, 10. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.softx.2019.100331>
- Andre T. (2023). *Apports de l'analyse spatiale à la recherche des sources et à la modélisation des réseaux d'acquisition et d'échanges des géomatériaux préhistoriques : Exemple de l'application aux silicites et matières colorantes en Périgord*. Unpublished Master thesis. Muséum National d'Histoire Naturelle, Paris.
- Angevin R., Delvigne V. (2021). Le paradoxe des « territoires fluides » ou comment penser la frontière quand temps et espace sont discontinus ? L'éclairage des sociétés magdaléniennes de France centrale (XVIe-XIIIe millénaires av. J.-C.). In: Mevel L., Weber M.-J., Maier A. (2021). *En Mouvement : Mobilités des hommes, des objets et des idées pendant le Paléolithique supérieur européen, Actes de la séance commune de la Société préhistorique française et la Hugo Obermaier-Gesellschaft à Strasbourg (16–17 mai 2019)*. *Société préhistorique de France, Paris (Séances de la Société préhistorique française, 17)*, 71–99. https://www.prehistoire.org/offres/doc_inline_src/515/D_Angevin_Delvigne_rgb.pdf
- Aubry T., Luis L. (2015). Adaptation to Resources and Environments during the Last Glacial Maximum by Hunter-Gatherer Societies in Atlantic Europe. *Journal of Anthropological Research*, The University of Chicago Press, 71-4, 523–544. <https://www.jstor.org/stable/44503949>
- Beaudry M., Parno T. (2013). *Archaeologies of Mobility and Movement*. [10.1007/978-1-4614-6211-8](https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-4614-6211-8)
- Collar A., Coward F., Brughmans T., Mills B. J. (2015). Networks in Archaeology: Phenomena, Abstraction, Representatio, *Journal of Archaeological Method and Theory*, New York, 22, 1–32.
- Dayet L., Lebon M. (Eds.) (2022). *Rapport d'opération du PCR PIGMENT-HO : Pigmentothèque en Vallée de l'Homme et bassin Aquitain, Unpublished Rapport d'activité*.
- Delvigne V. (2016). *Géoressources et expressions technoculturelles dans le sud du Massif central au Paléolithique supérieur : des déterminismes et des choix*. Doctoral thesis. Université Bordeaux 1. <https://theses.hal.science/tel-01326945/>
- Delvigne V., Lafarge A., Fernandes P., Pesesse D., Angevin R., Bindon P., Langlais M., Piboule M., Queffelec A., Tufféry C., Raynal J.-P. (2021). Quels territoires en préhistoire ? Une analyse par réseaux de lieux pour penser l'espace au Paléolithique supérieur. In: Mevel L., Weber M.-J., Maier A. (2021). *En Mouvement : Mobilités des hommes, des objets et des idées pendant le Paléolithique supérieur européen, Actes de la séance commune de la Société préhistorique française et la Hugo Obermaier-Gesellschaft à Strasbourg (16–17 mai 2019)*. *Société préhistorique de France, Paris (Séances de la Société préhistorique française, 17)*, 27-69. https://www.prehistoire.org/offres/doc_inline_src/515/C_Delvigne_et_al_rgb.pdf
- Delvigne V., Raynal J.-P. (2021). Spaces, areas, routes, sites...: Reading Palaeolithic territories. In: Averbouth A., Goutas N., Méry S. (2021). *Nomad lives: From prehistoric times to the present day*. Paris, Muséum National d'Histoire Naturelle, 245-26. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/356508463_Spaces_areas_routes_sites_Reading_Palaeolithic_territories

- Delvigne V., Ducasse S., Constans G., Peschaux C., Primault J., Sanchez De La Torre M. (*in press*). Quelle spatialité pour les industries à lamelles à dos dextre marginal ? Apport de la pétrologie et de l'analyse de réseaux. In: Langlais M., et Ducasse S. (Dir.) (2024). *Contextualiser Lascaux, Acte des séances de la SPF*. Société préhistorique de France, Paris.
- Di Méo G. (1999). *Géographie sociale et territoires*. Nathan, Paris.
- Féblot-Augustins J., Perlès C. (1992). Perspectives ethnoarchéologiques sur les échanges à longue distance. *Ethnoarchéologie: justification, problèmes, limites. XII^e rencontres internationales d'archéologie et d'histoire d'Antibes*. Editions APDCA, Juan-les-Pins. pp.195-209.
https://www.researchgate.net/publication/313820719_Perspectives_ethnoarcheologiques_sur_les_echanges_a_longue_distance
- Fernandes P., Raynal J.-P., Tallet P., Tufféry C., Piboule M., Seronie-Vivien M., Seronie-Vivien M.-R., Turq A., Morala A., Affolter J., Millet D., Millet F., Bazile F., Schmidt P., Foucher P., Delvigne V., Liagre J., Gaillot S., Morin A., Moncel M.-H., Garnier J.-F., Leandri-Bressy C. (2013). Une carte et une base de données pour les formations à silex du sud de la France : un outil pour la pétroarchéologie. *PALEO. Revue d'archéologie préhistorique*, 24, 219–228.
<https://doi.org/10.4000/paleo.2633>
- Fernandes P., Delvigne V., Vaissie E., Raynal J.-P. (Eds.) (2022). *PCR Réseau de lithothèques en Auvergne-Rhône-Alpes, Unpublished Rapport d'activité*.
- Gowen M. K., de Smet T. S. (2020). Testing least cost path (LCP) models for travel time and kilocalorie expenditure: Implications for landscape genomics. *PLoS ONE*, 15-9.
<https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0239387>
- Gravel-Miguel C., Wren C. D. (2018). Agent-based least-cost path analysis and the diffusion of Cantabrian Lower Magdalenian engraved scapulae. *Journal of Archaeological Science*, 99, 1–9.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jas.2018.08.014>
- Herzog I. (2012). Least-cost Networks. *Archaeology in the Digital Era*, Southampton, 237–248.
https://www.homepages.ucl.ac.uk/~ucakche/agdank/agdankht2012/CAA2012_Least_cost_networks_IHerzog.pdf
- Herzog I. (2014). 'Least-cost Paths - Some Methodological Issues'. *Internet Archaeology*, 36.
https://intarch.ac.uk/journal/issue36/herzog_toc.html
- Herzog I. (2021). Issues in Replication and Stability of Least-cost Path Calculations. *Studies in Digital Heritage*, Bloomington, 5-2, 131–155.
<https://doi.org/10.14434/sdh.v5i2.33796>
- Husdal J. (2000). *How to make a straight line square: Network Analysis in Raster GIS with time-dependent cost variables*. Doctoral thesis. University of Leicester.
https://fr.scribd.com/fullscreen/17311156?access_key=key-1lwgbi3goolujklmctxn0
- Kantner J. (2012). Realism, reality, and routes: Evaluating cost-surface and cost-path algorithms. In: White D. A., Surface-Evans S. L. (Dir.) (2012). *Least Cost Analysis of Social Landscapes: Archaeological Case Studies*, University of Utah Press, pp.225–238.
<https://doi.org/10.13140/2.1.1765.4725>
- Kelly R. L. (2013). *The lifeways of hunter-gatherers: the foraging spectrum*. Cambridge University Press. New York (2nd ed.).

- Langlais M. (2020). Des segments chronoculturels au modèle archéo-stratigraphique du Magdalénien dans le Sud-Ouest français (21 000- 16 000 cal. BP). Paris, Société préhistorique française, In : Straus L.G., Langlais M. (Eds.), *Actes Du XVIIIe Congrès de l'UISPP (6 Juin 2018). Presented at the Corrélations chrono-stratigraphiques et interactions culturelles au cours du Magdalénien entre l'Espagne cantabrique et le Sud-Ouest de la France... et au-delà*, Société préhistorique de France, Paris, 109–135. <https://hal.science/hal-03006345>
- Langlais M., Sécher A., Constans G., Delvigne V., Grubert M., Laroulandie V., Petillon J.-M., Renou S., Rigaud S., Royer A., Flies J.-F. (in press). Combe- Cullier (Lacave, Lot) : une séquence exceptionnelle du Magdalénien au bord de la Dordogne lotoise. *Gallia Préhistoire*.
- Leroi-Gourhan A. (1964). *Le geste et la parole. Tome I : Techniques et langage*, Albin Michel, Paris.
- Lussault M. (2013) *Spatialité*. In: Lévy et Lussault, *Dictionnaire de géographie, Dictionnaire de géographie*, Belin, Paris, 947-950.
- Martin-Jarque S., Herrero-Alonso D., Tarrío A., Lopez-Tascon C., Prieto A., Bécares J., Alvarez-Fernandez E. (2022). Determination of lithic raw materials in Cantabrian Spain during Greenland Stadial 2: The Magdalenian of Tito Bustillo Cave (Ribadesella, Asturias). *Journal of Archaeological Science: Report*. 46. <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S2352409X22003418>
- McLean A., Rubio-Campillo X. (2022). Beyond Least Cost Paths: Circuit theory, maritime mobility and patterns of urbanism in the Roman Adriatic. *Journal of Archaeological Science*, 138. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jas.2021.105534>
- Minetti G. C., Ferretti G., Moia C., Roi G. S., Susta D. (2006). Energy Cost of Walking and Running at Extreme Uphill and Downhill Slopes. *Journal of Applied Physiology: Respiratory, Environmental and Exercise Physiology*, 93, 1039–1046. <https://doi.org/10.1152/jappphysiol.01177.2001>
- Murrieta-Flores P. (2010). Traveling in a Prehistoric Landscape: Exploring the Influences that Shaped Human Movement. In: Frischer, B., Webb Crawford J., Koller D. (Eds.) (2010). *Making History Interactive. Computer Applications and Quantitative Methods in Archaeology (CAA). Proceedings of the 37th International Conference, Williamsburg, Virginia, United States of America*. Archaeopress, Oxford, 249 – 267. <https://doi.org/10.30861/9781407305561>
- Parcero-Oubina C., Smart C., Fonte J. (2023). « Remote Sensing and GIS Modelling of Roman Roads in South West Britain ». *Journal of Computer Applications in Archaeology*, 6-1, 62–78. <https://doi.org/10.5334/jcaa.109>
- Poupeau G., Le Bourdonnec F.-X., Bellot-Gurlet L. (2023). Caractérisation et circulation de l'obsidienne. In: Dillmann P., Bellot-Gurlet L. (2023). *Circulation et provenance des matériaux dans les sociétés anciennes. La contribution des méthodes archéométriques*, Éditions des Archives Contemporaines, Paris, 9–33.
- Prieto A., Garcia-Rojas M., Sanchez A., Calvo A., Domínguez-Ballesteros E., Ordoño J., García-Collado M. I. (2016). Stones in Motion: Cost units to understand flint procurement strategies during the Upper Palaeolithic in the south-western Pyrenees using GIS. *Journal of Lithic Studies*, 3-1, pp. 133-160. <https://doi.org/10.2218/jls.v3i1.1310>
- Sanchez de la Torre M., Mangado X. (2016). Where are they coming from? Procurement of siliceous sedimentary rocks in the Magdalenian open-air site of Montlleo (Prats i Sansor,

- Lleida). *Trabajos De Prehistoria*, 73, pp. 7-28.
<https://tp.revistas.csic.es/index.php/tp/article/view/713>
- Sanchez de la Torre M., Rafart E., Gonzales-Ovivares C., Gratuze B., Mangado X. (2025). Long-distance movements during the Last Glacial Maximum in the Pyrenean mountain Range: Fresh insights for Montlleó archaeological site (Prats i Sansor, Cerdanya, Spain). *Journal of Archaeological Science: Reports*. Journal of Archaeological Science: Reports. 61.
<https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S2352409X24005339#b0015>
- Surface-Evans S. & White D.A.. (2012). *Least Cost Analysys of Social Landscapes. Archaeological Case Studies*, University of Utah Press, Salt Lake City.
- Tobler W. (1993). Three Presentations on Geographical Analysis and Modeling: Non-Isotropic Geographic Modeling; Speculations on the Geometry of Geography; and Global Spatial Analysis. *UC Santa Barbara: National Center for Geographic Information and Analysis*. 93-1.
https://escholarship.org/content/qt05r820mz/qt05r820mz_noSplash_8f1f13a718ba4a0db0079773ffa4a7af.pdf
- Tufféry C., Delvigne V., Fernandes P. (2018). Combinaison d'un SMA et d'un SIG pour aider à la prospection pétroarchéologique. Exploration d'une approche multi-agents dans la modélisation des parcours naturels du silex. *ISTE*, London. [10.21494/ISTE.OP.2018.0276](https://doi.org/10.21494/ISTE.OP.2018.0276)
- Tufféry C. (2022). *Ce que le numérique fait à l'archéologie et aux archéologues. Contribution historiographique et épistémologique à l'étude des évolutions d'une discipline et de ses pratiques en France depuis les années 1970*. Doctoral thesis. CY Cergy Paris Université.
<https://theses.fr/2022CYUN1129>
- Tufféry C., Delvigne V., Fernandes P., Garniaux J. (2022). Protocole de préparation et de republication des données du BRGM sur les formations à silicites, *Préhistoires Méditerranéennes*, 7–14. <https://doi.org/10.4000/pm.3483>
- Uitermark J., Van Meeteren M. (2021). Geographical network analysis. *Tijdschrift voor Economische en Sociale Geografie*, Royal Dutch Geographical Society, Amsterdam, 112–4, 337–350. <https://doi.org/10.1111/tesg.12480>
- Vaissié E. (2021). Mobility of Paleolithic Populations: Biomechanical Considerations and Spatiotemporal Modelling. *PaleoAnthropology*, 1, pp. 120–144.
<https://doi.org/10.48738/2021.iss1.73>
- Van Leusen M. (1993). Cartographic modelling in a cell-based GIS. In: Andresen, J., Madsen T., Scollar I., Computing the Past. Computer Applications and Quantitative Methods in Archaeology. CAA92, University Press, Aarhus, 105–124.
https://proceedings.caaconference.org/paper/11_leusen_caa_1992/
- Verhagen P., Polla S., Frommer I. (2014). Finding Byzantine junctions with Steiner trees. In: Polla S, Verhagen P (eds) (2024). *Computational approaches to the study of movement in archaeology. Theory, practice and interpretation of factors and effects of long term landscape formation and transformation*. De Gruyter, Berlin, pp 73–98. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-04576-0_11
- Verhagen P., Nuninger L., Mark G. (2019). Modelling of pathways and movement networks in archaeology: an overview of current approaches. In: Verhagen P., Nuninger L., Mark G. (Eds.) (2019). *Finding the limits of the limes: modelling economy, demography and transport at the Edge of the Roman Empire*, Springer, pp.217-249. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-04576-0_11

White D.A. (2015). The Basics of Least Cost Analysis for Archaeological Applications. *Advances in Archaeological Practice*, 3, pp. 407-414. . <https://doi.org/10.7183/2326-3768.3.4.407>

Whitley T. & Hicks L. M. (2003). A geographic information systems approach to understanding potential prehistoric and historic travel corridors. *Southeastern Archaeology*, 22, pp. 77-91.